

Studies in the Cyclohexane Series Part XI. Friedel-Crafts Condensation of the Anhydrides of cis- and trans-1-Carboxy-4-methylcyclohexane-1-acetic acids with Aromatic Hydrocarbons and the Synthesis of 3-Methyl-8,9-and Substituted 8,9-benzo-spiro (5,5) undecanes

H. S. BAJAJ, R. D. DESAI and G. S. SAHARIA

Department of Chemistry, University of Delhi, Delhi-110007

Manuscript received 28 June 1974 ; revised 20 September 1974 ; accepted 17 October 1974

The anhydrides of cis- and trans-1-carboxy-4-methyl cyclohexane-1-acetic acids on condensation with aromatic hydrocarbons in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride furnish the respective $\alpha\alpha$ -(4'-methylcyclohexane)- β -aroyl propionic acids, which on subsequent reduction yield $\alpha\alpha$ -(4'-methylcyclohexane)- γ -aryl butyric acids. These on cyclisation with PPA and subsequent reduction give 3-methyl-8,9 and substituted 8,9-benzo-spiro (5,5) undecanes.

THOUGH work on the condensation of the anhydrides of $\alpha\alpha$ -cycloalkane succinic acids with aromatic hydrocarbons under Friedel-Crafts reaction conditions has been reported^{1,2}, but hardly any work to investigate the effect of substituted cyclohexyl group has been carried out except that of the condensation of the anhydrides of 1-carboxy 4-, 3-, and 2-methylcyclohexane-1-acetic acids with benzene³, where the authors have only reported these reactions without separating the acids into their isomeric forms.

The present communication describes the condensation of the anhydrides of the isomeric cis- and trans-

1-carboxy-4-methylcyclohexane-1-acetic acids⁴ with benzene, toluene and isomeric xylenes. The main object of this work was to study the effect of the substituted cyclohexane ring when present in the α -position of the anhydride and also to compare with the effect of the substituted cyclohexane ring when present in the α -position of the anhydride and also to compare with the effect of other unsubstituted and substituted cycloalkane rings on the course of the Friedel-Crafts reaction. In all these cases only one $\alpha\alpha$ -(4'-methylcyclohexane) β -aroyl propionic acid of the type II (X=O) was obtained^{2,5}; oxidation of these keto acids with sodium hypobromite furnished the

respective aromatic acids, melting points of which were undepressed with authentic samples. These keto acids on reduction gave the corresponding $\alpha\alpha$ -(4-methylcyclohexane)- γ -aryl butyric acids of the type II ($X=H_2$) adopting the methods of reduction indicated in Table 2; characterisation of II ($X=O$ and H_2) was made by their equivalent weights, analytical and IR spectral data and 2, 4-DNPs of the former. Cyclisation of II ($X=H_2$) with PPA⁵ furnished the 3-methyl-8, 9-and substituted 8, 9-benzo-10-keto-spiro (5, 5) undecanes of the type III ($X=O$) characterised through their 2, 4-DNPs and IR peaks (Table 3). Subsequent reduction of the spiro-ketones employing modified Clemmensen's method yielded the 3-methyl-8, 9-and substituted 8, 9-benzo-spiro (5, 5) undecanes of the type III ($X=H_2$) entered in Table 4.

Both the keto and the reduced acids were accompanied by neutral products^{1,2,6} of the types IV and V respectively which were assigned these structures based on their analytical and IR spectral data. The former was obtained in larger proportions during the condensation of the anhydride (I) with isomeric xylenes; however, by adjusting the reaction conditions it was possible to reduce their yields. Wolff-Kishner's modified method¹ was not found suitable for the above reductions as larger amounts (~ 88%) of a neutral product of the type VI were obtained^{1,9,10}.

Thus, from a study of the Table 3 and 4, it is observed that the boiling point of the cyclic ketones and the spiro-hydrocarbons of the A series are lower than those of the B series and the refractive indices of these products of A series are higher than those of the B series. This seems to be in agreement with the modified Auwers-Skita rule thereby indicating that the methyl group maintains its equatorial character in the case of both the above compounds. The axial character of the methyl group in both these compounds of the B series is also maintained with the exception of the cyclic ketone and the spiro

hydrocarbon prepared from m-xylene where these have higher boiling points as demanded by the rule but have got higher refractive indices against the expected lower values. This divergence may be regarded as an exception to the modified Auwers-Skita rule.

Experimental

Trans-1-Carboxy 4-methylcyclohexane-1-acetic acid m. p. 173° on refluxing with acetic anhydride furnished the anhydride m. p. 107° (lit. 104°) in 90% yield; the cis-analogue m. p. 137° furnished the anhydride m. p. 77° (lit 77°)¹¹.

Synthesis of 3-methyl 8, 9 and substituted 8, 9-benzo-spiro (5,5) undecanes. $\alpha\alpha$ -(4'-methylcyclohexane)- β -aroyl propionic acids: A solution of the anhydride (6.0 g; 0.033 mol) in dry hydrocarbon (35 ml) was cooled (-5°), anhydrous aluminium chloride (9.7 g; 0.072 mol) added in small lots with constant shaking during an hour and the contents, after keeping in an ice-salt bath for 4 hr, left at room temperature for 24 hr. The reaction mixture was heated in an oil bath (50°-60°) for 3 hr, decomposed with dilute hydrochloric acid, excess of the hydrocarbon steam distilled and the deposited solid filtered. The residue was refluxed with aqueous sodium hydroxide (5%; 400 ml) and the alkaline solution on acidification gave a solid, which on crystallisation from benzene-pet. ether (60°-80°) furnished $\alpha\alpha$ -(4'-methylcyclohexane)- β -aroyl propionic acids, and all the acids obtained from both the trans- and cis-acid anhydrides are entered in Table 1.

$\alpha\alpha$ -(4'-methylcyclohexane)- γ -butyric acids: $\alpha\alpha$ -(4'-Methylcyclohexane)- β -aroyl propionic acids (5.2 g) were reduced by Clemmensen or modified Clemmensen method (as indicated by Y or X in Table 2) by refluxing the contents for 50-60 hr. and addition of fresh quantities concentrated hydrochloric acid (5 ml) every 5 hr. The reaction products on working up in the normal manner gave pure $\alpha\alpha$ -(4'-methylcyclohexane)- γ -butyric acids either as a solid or liquid and these are given in Table 2.

TABLE 1— $\alpha\alpha$ -(4'-METHYLCYCLOHEXANE)- β -AROYL PROPIONIC ACIDS

Aroyl	M.P. °C	Yield %	Eq. wt. (mono- basic)	Mol. formula	Analysis				2,4-DNP °C	
					Found %		Requires%			
					C	H	C	H		
1. Benzoyl	A	165	87.4	259.8	$C_{18}H_{20}O_2$	73.5	7.7	73.8	7.7	228
	B	144	81.6	260.0		73.6	7.7			217
2. 4-Methylbenzoyl	A	168	88.5	274.2	$C_{17}H_{22}O_2$	74.4	8.0	74.5	8.0	167
	B	171	77.4	274.0		74.4	7.9			254
3. 3,4-Dimethylbenzoyl	A ⁺	142	84.2	288.0	$C_{18}H_{24}O_2$	75.0	8.1	75.0	8.3	216
	B	172	79.9	287.9		75.0	8.0			222
4. 2,4-Dimethylbenzoyl	A	161	82.1	287.8	"	75.0	8.0	"	"	310
	B	141	84.2	288.0	"	74.9	8.2	"	"	235
5. 2,5-Dimethylbenzoyl	A	121	85.3	288.1	"	75.1	8.3	"	"	230
	B	138	82.1	288.0	"	75.0	8.2	"	"	186

†Lactone of $\alpha\alpha$ -(4'-methylcyclohexane)- $\beta\gamma$ -unsaturated- γ -hydroxy-3,4-dimethylphenyl butyric acid, m.p. 152° (Found: C, 80.2; H, 8.1. $C_{18}H_{22}O_2$ requires C, 80.0; H, 8.2%). IR γ_{max}^{Nujol} 1795 cm^{-1}

A represents trans-series
B ,, cis-series

TABLE 2— $\alpha\alpha$ -(4'-METHYLCYCLOHEXANE)- γ -ARYL BUTYRIC ACIDS

Aryl	Conditions of reduction	M.P/b.p. °C	Yield %	Eq.wt. (mono-basic)	Mol. formula	Analysis				
						Found%		Requires%		
						C	H	C	H	
1. Phenyl	A	X	67	85.4	246	C ₁₆ H ₂₂ O ₂	78.2	8.9	78.1	8.9
	B	"	135	81.3	245.8	"	78.0	8.9	"	"
2. 4-Methylphenyl	A	"	215	23.0	259.8	C ₁₇ H ₂₄ O ₂	78.4	9.1	78.5	9.2
	B	"	100	87.9	260.0	"	78.4	9.0	"	"
3. 3,4-Dimethylphenyl	A [†]	"	103	6.4	274.2	C ₁₈ H ₂₆ O ₂	78.8	9.6	78.8	9.5
	A	Y	103	76.6	274.0	"	78.9	9.5	"	"
4. 2,4-Dimethylphenyl	B	X	167-9/2 mm	57.5	274.1	"	78.6	9.5	"	"
	A	Y	200	74.8	274.0	"	78.6	9.5	"	"
5. 2,5-Dimethylphenyl	B	X	114	73.0	273.9	"	78.6	9.4	"	"
	A	Y	97	71.2	274.0	"	78.9	9.5	"	"
"	B	X	210-12/4.5 mm	70.2	274.0	"	78.5	9.5	"	"

[†]Lactone of $\alpha\alpha$ -(4'-Methylcyclohexane)- γ -hydroxy- γ -3,4-dimethylphenyl butyric acid, m. p. 254°

(Found : C, 79.2 ; H, 8.8. C₁₈H₂₄O₂ requires C, 79.2 ; H, 8.8% ; IR $_{\max}^{\text{Nujol}}$ 1780 cm⁻¹)

X=modified Clemmensen method

Y=Clemmensen method

TABLE 3—3-METHYL-8,9-AND SUBSTITUTED 8,9-BENZO-10-KETO-SPIRO (5,5) UNDECANES

Substituent in the benzene ring	B.P. °C	Yield %	Ref. index	Mol. formula	Analysis				2,4-DNP °C	
					Found%		Requires%			
					C	H	C	H		
1. R ₁ =R ₂ =R ₃ =R ₄ =H	A	125/11 mm	72.4	n _D ²⁰ 1.5710	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ O	84.3	8.7	84.2	8.8	>300
	B	140-1/2 mm	65.8	n _D ^{20.5} 1.5380	"	84.0	8.7	"	"	300
2. R ₁ =R ₃ =R ₄ =H; R ₂ =CH ₃	A	158/12 mm	70.2	n _D ^{20.5} 1.5662	C ₁₇ H ₂₂ O	84.1	9.1	84.3	9.1	297(d)
	B	140/2.5 mm	70.3	—	"	84.1	9.0	"	"	227
3. R ₁ =R ₄ =H; R ₂ =R ₃ =CH ₃	A	145-6/1.5 mm	64.2	n _D ²² 1.5600	C ₁₈ H ₂₄ O	84.3	9.3	84.4	9.4	257
	B	180-1/4.5 mm	72.3	n _D ²⁷ 1.5525	"	84.2	9.3	"	"	141
4. R ₁ =R ₃ =H; R ₂ =R ₄ =CH ₃	A	140-1/7.5 mm	62.5	n _D ²⁴ 1.5400	"	84.6	9.4	"	"	243
	B	145-7/3 mm	74.2	n _D ²⁴ 1.5500	"	84.2	9.5	"	"	226.7
5. R ₂ =R ₃ =H; R ₁ =R ₄ =CH ₃	A	140/2.5 mm	62.5	n _D ¹⁸ 1.5510	"	84.3	9.5	"	"	254
	B	165-7/4.5 mm	66.4	n _D ²⁸ 1.5418	"	84.6	9.2	"	"	142

Substituent in the benzene ring

1. R ₁ =R ₂ =R ₃ =R ₄ =H	A	112/2.5 mm	74.8	n _D ^{28.5} 1.5515	C ₁₈ H ₂₂	89.6	10.3	89.7	10.3
	B	122/3.5 mm	70.0	n _D ²⁴ 1.5412	"	89.6	10.3	"	"
2. R ₁ =R ₃ =R ₄ =H; R ₂ =CH ₃	A	125-6/1.5 mm	53.0	n _D ¹⁸ 1.5600	C ₁₇ H ₂₂	89.4	10.5	89.5	10.5
	B	125-6/3 mm	83.3	n _D ²³ 1.5290	"	89.3	10.4	"	"
3. R ₁ =R ₄ =H; R ₂ =R ₃ =CH ₃	A	102/0.25 mm	57.9	n _D ²⁴ 1.5420	C ₁₈ H ₂₆	89.3	10.6	89.3	10.7
	B	195-6/13 mm	60.3	n _D ²⁸ 1.5348	"	89.2	10.6	"	"
4. R ₁ =R ₃ =H; R ₂ =R ₄ =CH ₃	A	127-8/5 mm	62.0	n _D ²⁴ 1.5358	"	89.3	10.5	"	"
	B	125-7/2.5 mm	74.4	n _D ²⁹ 1.5418	"	89.2	10.6	"	"
5. R ₂ =R ₃ =H; R ₁ =R ₄ =CH ₃	A	110-1/3.5 mm	70.2	n _D ²² 1.5564	"	89.3	10.6	"	"
	B	160/12.5 mm	66.1	n _D ²⁸ 1.5288	"	89.2	10.6	"	"

3-Methyl-8, 9-and substituted 8, 9-benzo-10-keto-spiro (5, 5) undecanes : $\alpha\alpha$ -(4'-Methylcyclohexane) γ -butyric acids (2.46 g) dissolved in PPA (prepared from phosphorus pentoxide, 15.0 g and ortho phosphoric acid, 10 ml) were heated in an oil bath at 180-200° for 2 hr with occasional shaking. The contents were poured over crushed ice (450 g), stirred and extracted with ether, the ethereal layer washed successively with aqueous sodium hydroxide (5% ; 2 \times 50 ml) and water ; the ethereal layer was dried (Na_2SO_4), ether recovered and the residue on distillation gave *3-methyl-8, 9-and substituted 8, 9-benzo-10-keto-spiro (5,5) undecanes* which are entered in Table 3.

3-Methyl 8, 9-and substituted 8, 9-benzo-spiro-(5,5) undecanes. 3-Methyl 8, 9-and substituted 8, 9-benzo-10-keto-spiro-(5,5) undecanes (1.14 g) were reduced by modified Clemmensen method employing amalgamated zinc (60 g), concentrated hydrochloric acid (100 ml), toluene (5 ml) and glacial acetic acid (2 ml) and refluxing the contents for 60 hr ; fresh quantities of concentrated hydrochloric acid (5 ml) were added every 6 hr. The reaction mixture was worked up in the customary manner and pure *3-methyl-8, 9-and substituted 8, 9-benzo-spiro (5, 5) undecanes* obtained by distillation under reduced pressure are given in Table 4.

References

1. G. S. SAHARIA and B. R. SHARMA., *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1962, **21B**, 547 ; *Indian J. Chem.*, 1963, **1**, 210.
2. R. D. DESAI and M. A. WALL., *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1937, **6A**, 135, 144.
3. S. C. SEN GUPTA and A. MITRA., *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **40**, 615.
4. H. S. BAJAJ, R. D. DESAI, J. M. SAGAR and G. S. SAHARIA., *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974 **51**, 624.
5. K. C. MATHUR and G. S. SAHARIA., *Indian J. Chem.*, 1964, **2**, 358.
6. A. T. BLOMQUIST and F. JAFFE., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 3405.
7. A. ALI, R. D. DESAI, R. F. HUNTER and S. M. M. MUHOMMAD., *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 1013.
8. R. N. MARVEL and A. O. GEISZIER., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 1259.
9. H. FISCHER, H. BEYER and E. ZAUCKER., *Ann.*, 1931, **486**, 55.
10. G. S. SAHARIA and M. P. TYAGI., *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1971, **48**, 467.
11. R. D. DESAI, R. F. HUNTER, GHULAM KHAN and G. S. SAHARIA., *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 416.